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OBJECTIVE NEED FOR THE FORMATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST COMPLEXES IN THE REGIONS

Homidov Kakhkhorali Kurbonali ugli
The researcher of Fergana state university

Annotation

This article explores the fact that the sustainable development of tourist complexes at the national level implies a social orientation that allows the local population to meet the necessary needs of today's generations living in the near future in order to improve the quality of life, economic development and the effective, environmentally friendly development of the territory in the future.

Keywords

Sustainable development, tourist complex, tourist specialization, development model, natural resource potential.

Currently, the need to move to a stable type of development is becoming more and more important and relevant. This fully applies to the sustainable development of tourist complexes and, as a result, tourism as a whole. The process of forming a model of sustainable development of tourist complexes is aimed at realizing the need and opportunities for the existence of a system of "man – Society – nature" and, ultimately, the implementation of the national interests of almost any country.

Nevertheless, the issues of scientific justification of the mechanisms of the transition to sustainable development of tourist complexes require additional research. One of the pressing problems of sustainable development is the elimination of contradictions that arise in the interaction between the economy and the ecology of tourist complexes. Tourist complexes, including Resort and wellness routes, have a number of distinctive features, which are primarily associated with the potential of the natural resource and the conditions of its development, which determine their functional purpose and specialization. The state of the natural environment is a supporting factor in the development of Tourism and, as a result, in the development of territorial entities that require the development of a model of transition to sustainable development.

Thus, at present, there is no single approach to the definition of the concept of "sustainable development of tourist complexes", which is due to the versatility of the translation of this term, as well as its use in systems of various levels of tourist specialization.

As noted above, there is currently no generally accepted translation of the term "sustainable development". This is due to many interpretations of this concept from different languages of the world. Many interpretations of the term "sustainable development" have led to conflicting views of scientists on the essence of the concept of "sustainable development of tourist complexes". This is because:

1. That the interpretation of this term is conditional;
2. There are no single approaches to the relationship between the concepts of "stability of the development of tourist complexes" and "stability of the development of tourist areas".

The classic definition of the term "sustainable development" was established in the mid-80s by the International Commission on Environment and development, which gives a tariff: "sustainable development is a development that meets the needs of the present, but does not pose a threat to the

ability of future generations to meet their needs." This important interpretation of the term being analyzed is inherently systematic, with limitations on natural resources, as well as the interaction of the anthroposystem and the biosphere.

In addition, some scholars now conclude that "there can be no stability in development because development denies stability". This is how the term stability meant the ability of territorial systems to return to a state of equilibrium after the internal and external environment had different effects on it. At the same time, the term development refers to the changes that occur in these systems.

At the same time, other researchers also show a positive trend in the growth and development of various subsystems of tourist complexes, indicating a close relationship between these categories. However, we believe that the stability of the development of tourist complexes does not determine the presence or absence of changes in systems.

The development of tourist complexes can be considered sustainable if the territory of tourist specialization achieves the effective functioning of the territorial system for a long time, providing a balance with the needs of society in order to improve its level and quality of life, prevent environmental degradation and maintain the ecosystem.

The main characteristic features of the sustainable development of tourist complexes can be identified:

1. One of the main signs of the sustainable development of tourist complexes is quantitative and qualitative changes in three interconnected directions - economic, social and environmental, taking into account the possibilities of activating the entrepreneurial activity of tourist organizations in a particular area. Based on this, it is possible to determine the corresponding types of stability of territories:

1.1. Economic, its purpose is to form a competitive economy of tourist complexes with natural resource potential and rational management of resource-saving technologies;

1.2. Aimed at improving the level and quality of life of the population of social, tourist complexes, the stability of social and cultural systems;

1.3. Environmental aims to prevent environmental degradation by ensuring the integrity of the natural system, its ability to self-medicate and adapt to changing conditions.

2. A distinctive feature of sustainable development is that the central idea of its implementation is to take care of future generations, as well as take into account environmental restrictions on the economic activity of people and tourist organizations.

3. Sustainable development can only be achieved by providing sustainable, coordinated activities and developing economic, social and environmental orientations.

Literature

1. Хомидов, Х. (2023). Худудларда туристик мажмуалар фаолиятини шакиллантириш ва тизимли бошқариш асосида худудлар туристик салоҳиятидан самарали фойдаланиш масалалари. " Milliy iqtisodiyotni isloh qilish va barqaror rivojlantirish istiqbollari" respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to 'plami., 412-415.

2. Хомидов, К. (2022). Повышение доходов производителей.

3. Khomidov, K. (2023). Characteristics of improving organizational and economic mechanisms of management in higher education institutions. Publishing House "Baltija Publishing".

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4. Xomidov, Q. (2018). Ускоренно развивающиеся отрасли экономики Республики Узбекистан. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
5. Homidov, K. K. U. (2022). Issues of ensuring food security in Uzbekistan. Scientific Impulse, 1(4), 1529-1534.
6. Юлдашева, Г. А., & Хамидов, К. (2022). Процессы модернизации системы бухгалтерского учета на предприятиях. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 230-231.
7. Homidov, K. K. U. (2022). Improvement of Organizational and Economic Mechanisms of Management in Food Industry Enterprises in Innovative Development of the Economy. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(11), 50-55.
8. Xomidov, Q. (2019). Цифровая экономика-путь к совершенству. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
9. Ўғли, Х. Қ. Қ. (2022). Ўзбекистонда озиқ-овқат хавфсизлиги таъминлаш масалалари. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(13), 10-15.
10. Xomidov, Q. (2019). Кластер-действенный инструмент конкурентоспособности региона. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
11. Xomidov, Q. (2020). Iqtisodiyotni investitsiyaviy jozibadorligini oshirishda erkin iqtisodiy zonalarini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
12. Xomidov, Q. (2019). Iqtisodiyotimizni raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda innovatsion tadbirkorlikning o'rni va ahamiyati. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
13. Xomidov, Q. (2019). Aholi bandligi ta'minlash-iqtisodiy munosabatlarning muhim omili. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
14. Akhmedova, N. K., & ugli Homidov, K. K. (2022). Institutional Basis of Digitalization of Management Activity of Food Industry Enterprises in Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(11), 34-38.
15. Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Socioeconomic characteristics of employment in Uzbekistan. *Инновационная наука*, (7-8), 64-66.
16. Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Перспективный комплекс экономики Узбекистана. In *Современная мировая экономика: проблемы и перспективы в эпоху развития цифровых технологий и биотехнологии* (pp. 54-56).
17. Мирсодиков, А. Т. (2021). Бюллетень науки и практики. бюллетень науки и практики Учредители: Овечкина Елена Сергеевна, 7(10), 329-335.
18. Tursunaliyevich, M. A. (2022). Improving the Management Process of Logistic Chain Activity in Construction. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 3(3), 151-154.
19. Abdulla, M. (2022). Improving Cost Management Processes in Construction Logistics Chains. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 419-423.
20. Mirsodikov, A. (2023). Approaches to the essence of logistics structures and formation of logistics chain. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 383-388.
21. Мирсодиков, А., & Черданцев, В. П. (2020). Роль маркетинговой стратегии в повышении конкурентоспособности образовательных услуг. информационные системы и коммуникативные технологии в современном образовательном процессе, 50-56.
22. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2019). Совершенствование интегральной оценки механизма рекреационно-туристических объектов. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 5(2), 127-134.

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VOLUME 4, ISSUE 2, 2023

23. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2019). Оценка использования рекреационных возможностей на рынке туристических услуг. Региональная экономика: теория и практика, 17(5), 990-1002.
24. Mirzaev, A. T. (2020). Evaluation of innovation capacity resource components in effective management of recreational clusters on the basis of econometric analysis. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). India, 5(7), 131-137.
25. Mirzaev, A. T. (2018). The level of use of tourist attractions in the regions and the factors affecting them. Economics and Innovative Technologies, 2018(3), 19.
26. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Совершенствование системы электронного бронирования как часть цифровизации управленческой деятельности туристско-рекреационных предприятий. Бюллетень науки и практики, 6(8), 165-172.
27. Mirzaev, A. T. (2018). Estimation of the prospects for the use of recreational facilities in the market of tourism services. In Наука сегодня: вызовы, перспективы и возможности (pp. 76-77).
28. Mirzaev, A. T. (2020). Assessment of cluster formation in management of recreational activity. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 605-610.
29. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2019). Туристик-рекреация корхоналари фаолиятини бошқаришнинг иқтисодий самарадорлиги таҳлили. Иқтисодиёт ва таълим, 6, 194-199.
30. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Ўзбекистонда туристик-рекреация корхоналари фаолиятини бошқаришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Бизнес-Daily медиа, 1, 62-65.

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